

Magnetic and Dielectric Properties of Transition Elements Substituted Yttrium Iron Garnets

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Abstract

Yttrium iron garnet (YIG) is a natural choice for microwave devices [1]. We have successfully prepared polycrystalline samples of transition elements (Cr and Mn) substituted YIG in single-phase form. The lattice parameter is found to decrease with increase in concentration of doped transition elements. Room temperature saturation magnetization value is found to increase with increase in Cr and Mn concentrations. The analysis of impedance spectra shows the deviation of relaxation process from ideal Debye type. In Cr substituted YIG, both grains and grain boundaries are found to contribute while in Mn substituted YIG only grain boundaries are contributing towards the relaxation process. The value of dielectric constant at 1MHz is found to increase with increase in Cr concentration from the value of 20 for $x = 0$ to 52 for $x = 0.5$ while, in case of Mn substituted YIG the dielectric constant is found to slightly decrease to $\epsilon' = 13$ for $x = 0.2$. These samples show an anomaly in the vicinity of magnetic transition temperature which may be attributed to the magneto-electric coupling.

Keywords: Magnetic ceramics; yttrium iron garnet; saturation magnetization; impedance spectra;

References

1. E.J.J. Mallmann et al, Solid State Phenomena, 202 (2013) 65.